

A STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY INSPECTION METHOD OF HIGH STRENGTH RAIL STEELS FOR SCHEDULED MONITORING VIA MICRO INDENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Rail grinding is a critical maintenance process that restores worn railway tracks by removing irregularities and reshaping the rail profile. However, evaluating the load carrying capabilities of the rail steels for each pass such as hardness, yield strength, and fracture toughness can be very challenging since most non-destructive testing (NDT) approach cannot effectively measure these mechanical properties during maintenance. In this study, a novel technique for evaluating the fracture toughness and hardness, yield strength of high strength rail steels is introduced using spherical indentation method, based on a modified limit load analysis. This approach defines a crack-initiation point (CIP) within the fully plastic deformation region of the indentation, indicating the onset of a theoretically defined virtual crack. By combining this method with the J-integral, the fracture toughness (K_{JC}) is determined. However, localized hardening effects encountered necessitated the use of the expansion cavity model in conjunction with the modified limit load analysis to accurately estimate the indentation pressure-normalized depth curve, indentation plastic area (A_{pl}) and the CIP for fracture toughness evaluation. The evolution of the plastic zone beneath the surface of the rail steels was also examined, assessing its potential as a non-destructive testing (NDT) method, proffering the minimum indenter sizes required for structural integrity inspection for different rail grinding applications. Ultimately, spherical indenters proved effective in estimating fracture toughness, and the advantages and limitations of this method are discussed, highlighting its potential as a quick and reliable NDT technique for the railway industry in the future.

INTRODUCTION

The safe and smooth operation of railway networks centers critically on the integrity of the rail steel, which is a function of the track's roughness (Haji et al., 2022; Solano-Alvarez and Bhadeshia, 2024). Amongst different rail maintenance techniques, rail grinding as a cost-effective solution to the capital cost incurred in procuring rail tracks (Zarembski, 1988), which is a means of restoring the smooth-running surface of the rail and is a combination of both corrective and preventive maintenance schemes. Corrective rail grinding is employed to extend track lifespan by mitigating severe corrugations, deep cracks, transverse detail defects (Leishman et al., 2017) and other surface irregularities. This process effectively reduces dynamic loading, thereby decelerating the rate of rolling contact fatigue (RCF) and preventing catastrophic failures. Proactive scheduling of rail grinding is crucial for maintaining optimal rail profile, minimizing RCF initiation, and routinely eliminating minor surface

imperfections (Leishman et al., 2017; Mesaritis et al., 2023). These defects not only compromise ride quality and increase noise but also pose significant safety risks. Consequently, the frequency of rail grinding is determined by a complex interplay of factors, including traffic volume, axle loads, track curvature, and the specific steel grade employed. Rail grinding is crucial across various rail applications, comprising *heavy haul freight lines*, *high-speed passenger networks*, *urban transit systems*, and *conventional lines*, each with unique operational demands and wear patterns.

However, ensuring the long-term reliability of rail steel presents some significant challenges. While visual inspections and conventional non-destructive testing (NDT) methods provide valuable insights, the in-situ monitoring of critical mechanical properties, such as Modulus of elasticity, yield strength, hardness, and fracture toughness, along the rail network remains a formidable task owing the variability of mechanical properties from sections to sections in the rail network. This difficulty stems from several factors, including rails are often rooted in track structures, making it challenging to deploy traditional testing equipment (Okocha et al. 2023a; Yu et al., 2018a; Yu et al., 2018b; Okocha et al. 2024; Yu et al., 2023; Okocha et al. 2023b), rail lines are exposed to harsh environmental conditions, including temperature variations, moisture, and debris, which can interfere with measurement accuracy (He et al., 2023; Santa et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2020; Yelemessov et al., 2023), rail steel properties can vary significantly along the length of the rail due to manufacturing processes, welding, and in-service degradation (Sichani and Bezin, 2018; Messaadi et al., 2021), the sheer size and complexity of rail networks: The vast extent of railway infrastructure makes comprehensive monitoring logistically demanding and costly (Rong et al., 2021; Esveld and Esveld, 2021). Therefore, the ongoing development of advanced sensing technologies and non-destructive evaluation techniques is crucial for achieving a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of rail steel integrity and optimizing maintenance strategies. One recent method used for evaluating the integrity of high strength ductile structures is the micro indentation testing (Okocha et al. 2023a; Yu et al., 2018a; Yu et al., 2023; Okocha et al. 2023b; Okocha et al. 2025). The indentation test uses controlled depth and force data extracted from the local deformation of materials to evaluate critical mechanical parameters from elastic to plastic characteristics like the Young's modulus (E), yield strength($\sigma_{y,ind}$), Hardness(H_B), fracture toughness (K_{JC}). Since K_{JC} , σ_{ys} and H_B are paramount mechanical properties of the rail steel's contact surface needed to maintaining the integrity of the rail steels for a safe and smooth operation, this study will focus on these properties. In this study, indentation testing is conducted on four high strength rail steel to estimate the K_{JC} , $\sigma_{y,ind}$ and H_B while in addition compute the plastic zone development beneath the indenter (rail substructure) to suggest an optimal a pre-maintenance (inspection) approach before rail grinding maintenance and operation is carried out.

CRITICAL INDENTATION ENERGY FOR K_{JC} ESTIMATION

The fracture toughness also regarded as the critical stress intensity factor (K_{JC}) from J-integral is based on virtually determined J-integrals as expressed in Eq.1.

$$K_{JC} = \lim_{a_c \rightarrow a_c} \sqrt{\frac{J \cdot E_s}{(1-\nu_s)}} \quad (1)$$

$$J = J_e + \frac{J_p}{f(\eta_{avg})} = \frac{(1-\nu_s^2)}{E_s} \cdot \left(\frac{L'}{2a_c' \sqrt{\pi a_c'}} \right)^2 + \frac{\eta_{pl}}{f(\eta_{avg})} \frac{A_{pl}}{\pi (a_c')^2} \quad (2)$$

where J is the virtual J-integral that consists of an elastic (J_e) and plastic (J_p) component derived from of the virtual load-displacement data, E_s the Young's modulus of the material, a_c' the virtual contact radius, A_{pl} the plastic area of the virtual load-depth curve, η_{pl} the plastic work factor that depends on the specimen geometry of spherical indenters taking as 0.983 (Okocha et al. 2025), L' the virtual load, and ν_s , the Poisson's ratio of the material as shown in Eq. (2). The stress triaxiality factor, $f(\eta_{avg})$ in the plastic component of the J-integral model is also considered. The value of $f(\eta_{avg})$ occurring during indentation is determined based on the concept of an average stress triaxiality (η_{avg}) as seen in Eq. (3), which reflects the evolution of η with the equivalent plastic strain.

$$\eta_{avg} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_{eq,CIP}^p} \int_0^{\varepsilon_{eq,CIP}^p} \eta(\varepsilon_{eq}^p) d\varepsilon_{eq}^p \quad (3)$$

where $\eta(\varepsilon_{eq}^p)$ is the evolution of η as a function of ε_{eq}^p , $\varepsilon_{eq,CIP}^p$, the equivalent plastic strain at the crack initiation point (CIP), which is the point during indentation regarded as the onset of a virtual crack (Okocha et al. 2024; Okocha et al. 2025).

The average triaxiality factor is expressed in Eq. (4) as a function of the Poisson's ratio of the specimen (ν_s) and η_{avg} .

$$f(\eta_{avg}) = \frac{2}{3}(1 + \nu_s) + 3(1 - 2\nu_s)(\eta_{avg}^2) \quad (4)$$

CIP AND INDENTATION VIRTUAL LOAD-DEPTH

The concept of the crack initiation point (CIP), developed through the foundational work of Miller (1988) and Shield (1955), defines the maximum load necessary to trigger fracture in a flawed structure. This concept is rooted in the behavior of an elastic-perfectly plastic material, where maximum plasticity is achieved under the load generated by a simple punch. Building upon this foundation, Kim et al. (2021) and Okocha et al. (2024) extended the CIP methodology by employing the von Mises failure criterion, in contrast to the Tresca criterion, when analyzing structures subjected to loads from flat-ended cylindrical indenters and spherical indenters. In this work, we will also consider the use of $\delta = 2.87$ for defining the pressure at CIP (P_{CIP}).

$$P_{CIP} = \frac{L_{CIP}}{\pi(a_c)^2} = \delta \cdot \sigma_y \quad (5)$$

where L_{CIP} is the load corresponding to the CIP, and a_c the contact radius corresponding to CIP via the spherical indentation in Eq.(5). To estimate fracture toughness using a single indentation loading, virtual spherical indenters of varying radii are employed to determine corresponding virtual loads and depths. The geometric relationship between these virtual depths and radii is defined by Eq. (6), which reveals that spherical indenters, irrespective of their size, yield a relatively consistent crack initiation point (CIP) and normalized depth (h/a_c).

$$\frac{h'}{a_c} = \left(\frac{h}{a_c} \right)_{CIP} \quad (6)$$

where h and a_c are the indentation depth and contact radius of the spherical indenter type while h' and a'_c , the pre-determined virtual indentation depth related to the virtual contact radius of the virtual spherical indenters, respectively. The average stress to take account of different indenter sizes is expressed in Eq. (7), which defines the average pressure over the contact region during indentation. According to the procedures in Okocha et al. (2025), after $(h/a_c)_{CIP}$ is attained, h' is taking as 0.2mm to 0.05mm in decreasing steps of 0.05mm to account for decreasing plastic contribution to the indentation loading by varying virtual indenter sizes. The different a'_c values forms the basis of attaining different J-integral values needed for K_{JC} estimation.

$$P = \frac{L}{\pi a_c^2} \quad (7)$$

MEASUREMENTS OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Yield Strength

Prior research on yield strength estimation through spherical indentation has primarily focused on analyzing material deformation behavior using the first derivative. This approach identifies changes in the slope of the indentation curve, which corresponds to transitions in the deformation regime of the elastic-plastic material. In this study, the indentation pressure (P) and normalized depth (h/a_c) were used to investigate its ability to estimate $\sigma_{y,ind}$ for high strength alloys based on the *full plasticity yielded pressure*, P_y .

$$\sigma_{y,ind} = \frac{P_y}{\delta} \quad \text{where } \delta = 2.87. \quad (8)$$

Indentation Hardness

Traditional hardness measurements (H_B) adhere to standards like ISO 6508 for Rockwell hardness (1999), and ISO 144577 for instrumented indentation test for hardness and materials parameters (2015). However, the research of hardness characterization, Gao et al. (2006a) and Gao et al. (2006b) presents an alternative approach, utilizing spherical indentation to analyze indentation hardness evolution. This method describes indentation deformations by focusing on the projected area, derived from an elastic-plastic solution based on the expansion cavity model (ECM). Specifically, Eq. (9) provides the exact solution, accounting for the absence of a strain gradient effect (Gao et al., 2006a and Gao et al., 2006b) due to the indenter sizes used, and assuming the material exhibits elastic-power-law hardening behavior. This aids in eliminating indentation size effect (ISE) that occurs in spherical indentation resulting in localized hardening and plasticity beneath the tip of the indenter during initial contact. Essentially, this approach offers a more detailed understanding of hardness by relating it to the deformation mechanisms occurring during spherical indentation.

$$H_{ECM} = \sigma_y \cdot \frac{2}{3} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{n} \left[\left(\frac{1}{4} \frac{E_s}{\sigma_y} \frac{a_c}{R} \right)^n - 1 \right] \right\} \quad (9)$$

where H_{ECM} is the indentation hardness via the spherical ECM, n , the strain hardening exponent, E_s , the Young's modulus of the material and R , the radius of the spherical indenter ($D=2R$).

A simple condition for H_B measurement as suggested in Okocha et al. (2025) from the estimation of H_{ECM} is attaining a critical H_{ECM} when $\frac{d(H_{ECM})}{d(a_c/R)} = H_{ECM}$. Eq. 10 shows the expression for H_B estimation from H_{ECM} .

$$H_B = 0.102\kappa C_{ys} \frac{H_{C,ECM}}{\delta} \quad (10)$$

$$C_{ys} = \lambda \left(2.845 - 0.4921 \frac{a_c}{R} \right) \quad \lambda = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{Tresca} \\ 2/\sqrt{3} & \text{von Mises} \end{cases}$$

where κ is a fitting parameter for the difference between $H_{ECM} - h/a_c$ with $P - h/a_c$ curves which is suggested to be caused by the additional force exerted experimentally due to frictional effect included in $P - h/a_c$ curve, κ is taken as ~ 1.13 for high strength rail steels while C_{ys} is the hardness constraint factor for finding the solutions to the pressure distribution of an elastic-plastic spherical indentation model.

EXPERIMENTS, MATERIALS, AND METHODS

Material of Study

The materials used in this study are high strength rail steels. Due to the confidentiality of the rail steels, their chemical compositions are not revealed. A total of four rail steels were used to estimate the mechanical properties and fracture toughness via standard test (Okocha et al. 2023a; Yu et al., 2018a). The rail, steels are surface heat treated except CZ rail steel, which is hot rolled and allowed to cool controllably during the manufacturing process.

Table 1 Rail samples and their microstructures

Rail Name / Identification number	Microstructure-heat treatment
JP	Deep head hardened
EV	Deep head hardened
CZ	-
Rail #1	Head hardened perlite

Rail Grinding Thickness Reduction and Rail Reprofilng

To extend the lifespan of rails and maintain the competitiveness and safety of railway transport, effective rail maintenance strategies are crucial. This includes not only selecting optimal steel grades and employing modern rail inspection methods but also utilizing appropriate rail grinding techniques. Different rail grinding principles offer varying levels of precision and material removal, which directly impact the minimum thickness that can be removed from a rail during reprofiling (Popović et al., 2022). While the selection of rail grinding principles is nuanced and context-dependent, general applications can be observed across different rail networks.

Rotating grinding, a versatile and widely employed method with a minimum material removal of approximately 0.5 mm, is frequently used for general maintenance and corrective grinding on *conventional lines*, as well as for significant material removal on *heavy haul freight lines* to address substantial wear, deep corrugation, and substantial plastic deformation.

Milling, which offers precise material removal (around 0.3 mm minimum) and is suitable for *complex rail profiles*, is favored in *urban transit systems* where noise and vibration control are paramount, and in high-speed passenger networks for maintaining precise rail geometry due to defects that require accurate shaping.

Oscillating grinding, focused on surface finish and minimizing material removal (approximately 0.2 mm minimum), is predominantly applied in *high-speed networks* to ensure smooth rail surfaces and reduce vibration, and for preventive maintenance where fine finishing is crucial (Popović et al., 2022).

High-speed grinding, emphasizing efficiency and preventive maintenance with minimal material removal (around 0.1 mm minimum), is utilized for rapid maintenance over long stretches of main lines and across various networks where minimizing track occupation time is essential and removal of defects like corrugation removal below the corrugation troughs and preventing the development of more severe damage, such as early-stage RCF.

Ultimately, *heavy haul freight lines* often rely on robust rotating grinding for significant material removal, *high-speed passenger networks* prioritize precision with milling and oscillating grinding, urban transit systems demand precise reprofiling with smooth finishes, and conventional lines utilize a mix of methods based on specific needs. The choice of grinding principle, therefore, hinges on a complex interplay of factors, necessitating a tailored approach to meet the unique demands of each rail network. The different rail grinding principles and approximate material removal are shown in Figure 1 (Popović et al., 2022; Steyn et al., 2024).

Figure 1 Different principles of rail grinding and an approximate value of minimum material removal

Standard Test and Indentation Testing

Standard tests were conducted from our previous works (Okocha et al. 2023a; Yu et al., 2018a; Yu et al., 2023; Okocha et al. 2023b; Okocha et al. 2025) following ASTM E8/E8M and ASTM E99 for mechanical properties and fracture toughness, respectively. To validate the proposed inspection methodology, laboratory-based spherical indentation tests were performed. A single indentation was conducted on each rail specimen, with the test setup and specimen dimensions detailed in Figure 2. These tests utilized an MTS machine and a series of tungsten carbide indenters, ranging in diameter from 1.19 mm to 6.35 mm. The tungsten carbide indenters, characterized by a Young's modulus of 630 GPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.21, were securely force-fitted into a 4140 heat-treated, stress-relieved (HTSR) steel component, which acted as an intermediate fixture between the machine grips. Pre-determined indentation depths were utilized in a quasi-static state to extract the required force per rail steel.

Figure 2. Schematics of the instrumented indentation test.

FE Modelling

Finite element (FE) modeling of the indentation tests, performed using ABAQUS/CAE 6.14 standard analysis, served two primary purposes: firstly, to estimate the average stress triaxiality (η_{avg}) within the material during indentation and to evaluate the extent at which plastic zone radius (c) at the rail steel’s substructure would evolve. The modelling, meshing and contact region was achieved following procedure in (Okocha et al., 2025). Figure 3 shows the FE modelling illustration, which was analysed like the experimental set-up as described in Fig 2. i.e. fixing the base of the material and applying pre-determined indentation depths in a quasi-static step.

Figure 3. FE modelling and mesh orientation of the indentation testing using a rigid indenter.

RESULTS

Standard Test Outcomes

A summary of the results standard tests for the mechanical properties and fracture toughness of the rail steels are summarized in table 2, which were conducted from the average values of three different specimens (Okocha et al. 2023a; Yu et al., 2018a; Yu et al., 2023; Okocha et al. 2023b).

Table 2: Mechanical properties and fracture toughness of the high strength rail steels.

Rail Name /Properties	E (MPa)	σ_y (MPa)	n	H_B (std. dev)	K_{IC} (MPa.m ^{0.5}) (std. dev)
JP	200,000	820	0.086	310 (28)	39.42 (1.44)
EV	197,000	714	0.085	330 (11)	41.73 (1.29)
CZ	195,000	648	0.082	260 (19)	34.32 (0.62)
Rail #1	185,000	943	0.05009	342 (28)	42.28 (1.33)

Indentation Loading and Unloading Cycles

The indentation load and unloading curve was conducted going in incremental steps for all the rail steels. Figure 4(a) shows the loading and unloading force-depth diagram for JP rail steel as an illustration using 3mm spherical indenter size while Figure 4(b) shows the load-depth curve of a single cycle using different indenter sizes for JP rail steel as an illustration. The difference in slope for the unloading curves at the same indentation depths in Figure 4(b) signifies the difference in damage imposed, which is signified by the degradation of the Young’s modulus.

Figure 4. Indentation loading and unloading cycle: (a) Typical spherical indentation loading-unloading cycles of JP using 1.19mm indenter size as an illustration and (b) Single indentation cycle of different indenter sizes.

Yield strength estimation via indentation

For the yield strength, Figure 5 (a) show the estimation of $\sigma_{y,ind}$ for JP rail steel as an illustration of other rail steels, where the initial portion of the average stress is truncated due to ISE during initial contact of the indenter with the substrate. The rail steel’s behavior mechanism is also described showing changes from ISE, average elastic regime, average plastic regime and to the diminishing strain hardening effect.

Figure 5. Yield strength estimation: (a) Typical spherical indentation illustration of JP using 1.19mm indenter size, and (b) Comparison between σ_y vs $\sigma_{y,ind}$.

Interestingly, another important point in the P'_{h/a_c} curve is the onset of large disturbances, which exhibits a rather relatively constant P'_{h/a_c} value with further indentation depths also regarded as a point of maximum shear stress (Okocha et al., 2025). Figure 5(b) show the variation of $\sigma_{y,ind}$ from different indenters with standard yield strength. The indentation estimates the $\sigma_{y,ind}$ which strongly correlates with conventional yield strength.

H_B Estimation via Indentation

By applying Eq. (9), the similarity of H_{ECM} and a_c/R as seen in Figure 6(a) between indenter sizes as seen in Figure 6 promotes the use of micro-indenters for the rail steel's inspection method before rail grinding as a non-destructive test. This adds to the advantage of spherical indentation than other indenter types for structural integrity assessment. For the estimation of H_B , Eq. (10) is applied by determining the $H_{C,ECM}$ from the evolution of H_{ECM} . The comparison between conventional H_B and indentation H_B attained from the H_{ECM} is shown in Figure 6(b).

Figure 6. Hardness estimation: (a) Typical spherical indentation illustration of JP using all indenter sizes, and (b) Comparison between conventional Brinell hardness and hardness estimated via ECM indentation approach

η_{avg} Estimation and Plastic Zone Size

As described in the FE modelling, the η_{avg} was estimated by extracting the evolution of η with the equivalent plastic strain captured at the element showing the most -ve η . Figure 7(a) shows the contour plot of the η variation as during the indentation loading. Another important estimation at CIP is the measurement of c . The vertical measurement from the contact surface, which is c , is also compared with the horizontal measurement, which is the a_c . Figure 7(b) shows an illustration of the spherical indenter indented on the rail head and the extent of the plastic zone size is being investigated. The c provides an insight to the limit at which rail grinding operation will be implemented after inspecting the rail steel's structural integrity.

Extent of plastic zone at the subsurface of the rail steel under inspection

Figure 7. Numerical indentation outcomes of JP as an illustration for other rail steels: (a) Stress triaxiality contour plot of the indentation testing, and (b) an illustration of the plastic zone size at CIP on the rail head

K_{JC} Estimation via Indentation

For the estimation of fracture toughness, to attain the virtual J-integral, L' and h'' curve must be defined. Following the procedures in Okocha et al., (2025). The virtual load, L' can be estimated as seen in Eq. (11).

$$L' = H_{C,ECM} \cdot \pi (a_c')^2 \quad (11)$$

The new virtual depth (h'') is expressed in Eq.(12)

$$h'' = \left(\frac{h}{a_c} \right) \cdot a_c' \quad (12)$$

The extrapolated K_J to a_c' is shown in Figure 8(a) as well as the comparison between K_{IC} and K_{JC} between the different rail steels are shown in Figure 8(b). The average and deviation by the indentation technique for K_{JC} estimations are provided showing the proximity with standard testing.

Figure 8. K_{JC} estimation using modified LLA: (a) K_{JC} for the four rail steels, and (b) comparing K_{JC} and K_{IC} Minimum Indenter Size (R) for Rail Inspection

In this study, the minimum indenter size required for rail inspection for estimating the rail's integrity is categorized into the rail gridding principles. Following FE modelling, the size of the plastic zone, c can be estimated for the different rail steels at CIP and correlated with the contact radius, a_c . Figure 9 shows the linear fit between c and a_c , which suggests an average of 2.64 as the constant value for fracture toughness estimation based on c/a_c .

Figure 9. K_{JC} estimation using modified LLA: (a) K_{JC} for the four rail steels, and (b) comparing K_{JC} and K_{IC}

Following the approach of the expanding cavity models for spherical indentation by Gao et al. (2006b), the radius of the indenter as expressed in Eq. (13) and taking the relationship between c and a_c in Fig. 9, a correlation can be evaluated between the thickness of removal, which in this study we suggest half of the plastic zone size as a safety factor ($c/2$). For this to be effective, indentation depth, h , must be considered using a fraction of the indenter radius ($0.045 \leq h/R \leq 0.055$) that estimates P_{CIP} .

$$\left(\frac{c}{a_c}\right)^3 = \frac{1}{4} \frac{E}{\sigma_y} \frac{a_c}{R} \quad (13)$$

From Fig. 9, we can deduce approximately that:

$$c = 2.64a_c - 0.03 \quad (14)$$

Hence the minimum indenter radius, R taking into account the mechanical property of the rail steel, E/σ_y and the geometrical correlation during indentation a_c/R as well as the depth of thickness removal based on the rail grinding principle with a *safety factor of 2* can be evaluated as Eq.(15) by combining Eqs. (13) and (14), where c is taken as the:

$$R = \frac{E}{\sigma_y} \left(\frac{c_{MMR} + 0.03}{5.28} \right) \left(0.379 + 0.011 / c_{MMR} \right)^3 \quad (15)$$

where c_{MMR} is the thickness of the minimum material removal based on the rail grinding principle to be implemented on the rail head after the consideration of safety factor has been applied.

RAIL INDENTATION PRE-INSPECTION, MERITS AND DEMETRITS

Rail Indentation Pre-Inspection

The rail grinding process begins with an initial assessment and planning phase, where engineers inspect the rail for wear, roughness, and surface defects using primarily visual inspection and conventional NDT. This is to evaluate whether the objective would be categorized into preventive maintenance, corrective grinding, or reprofiling. Based on the findings, an appropriate grinding method—such as rotating, milling, oscillating, or high-speed grinding—is selected. Essential parameters, including grinding depth and frequency, are established to maximize rail longevity. Additionally, the spherical indentation approach can be included in the entire process for mechanical property inspection to ensure structural integrity by measuring hardness for wear resistance, yield strength for load-bearing capacity, and fracture toughness for crack resistance. Current records can be compared to past records based on the scheduled maintenance set out by the rail grinding process. If the rail fails to meet the required mechanical properties or falls below a set-point, further assessment or replacement may be necessary. Fig. 10 shows an illustration detailing the steps for structural integrity inspection of the rail steels for scheduled monitoring.

Before execution, pre-operational preparations are undertaken to secure the work area, including setting up safety barriers, warning signals, and track possession agreements to minimize operational risks. Grinding equipment is inspected for functionality, while environmental considerations like dust and noise control are implemented. In the final verification stage, all safety measures and grinding parameters are cross-checked against industry standards.

Figure 10. Rail grinding planning and execution with inclusion pre-indentation inspection technique

Merits

- *Non-Destructive Testing (NDT)*: Spherical indentation permits for mechanical property assessment without substantially damaging the rail, hence, ideal for in-service inspections.
- *Assesses multiple mechanical properties*: The spherical indentation method provides estimates into K_{JC} , σ_{ys} and H_B , which are critical for rail integrity.
- *Localized Testing*: It enables the assessment of specific worn-out areas, ensuring targeted maintenance and even forensic assessment in the case of rail break.
- *Quick and Efficient*: Compared to full-scale tensile or fracture destructive tests, spherical indentation is relatively fast and does not require extensive sample preparation.
- *Portable Equipment* – The indentation approach can be made transportable and compact, making them ideal for direct application on tracks, reducing downtime for inspections.

Demerits

- *Limited Depth of Analysis*: Only surface or near-surface properties can be assessed, which may not reveal subsurface defects like internal cracks or deep material degradation.
- *Influence of Surface Conditions*: The accuracy of indentation readings can be affected by surface roughness, oxidation, or contaminants, necessitating proper surface preparation.
- *Limited Load-Bearing Simulation*: While it provides valuable hardness and strength data, it does not fully replicate complex loading conditions experienced by rails under dynamic train loads.
- *Requires Skilled Interpretation*: – The results depend on material-specific calibration and expertise in analyzing indentation data, increasing the need for specialized training and a rigorous data analysis.
- *Empirical Correlations Required*: Converting indentation results into useful mechanical property values (e.g., yield strength, fracture toughness) often relies on empirical models, which may introduce uncertainty.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, spherical indentation can be integrated into rail grinding scheduled maintenance activities to assess mechanical properties and ensure structural integrity. By incorporating this technique into scheduled rail grinding maintenance, it provides valuable data for monitoring rail steel's health, supporting long-term performance evaluation and reliability.

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